

Web-series and Indian Media: A Lethal Cocktail of Drugs, Sex and Violence

Dr. Rajesh Kumar

Associate Professor, P.P.N. College, Kanpur (Uttarpradesh)

shodhshree@gmail.com

Abstract

In recent years phenomenon of web-series has started dominating the entertainment scene. This paper makes content and discourse analysis of some of these web-series and concludes that these series are serving a cocktail of drugs, sex and violence to the viewers, who mostly belong to younger generation. Every dialogue is prefixed or suffixed by an expletive. There is a cult of glorification of crime and mafia dons are portrayed having Robin Hood like qualities. They take the path of crime, only because, society had left no option for them. Politicians use them and have them killed when they have served their purpose. This paper argues that these web-series are having tremendously negative effects on young minds. This paper suggests that these web-series should immediately be brought under the purview of Censor and people should refuse to watch such series. Parents need to become cautious about what the youngsters in the family are watching.

Keywords: *Web-series, Mafia, Don, Drugs, Sex, Violence, Expletives, Censor, Youngsters.*

Indian constitution grants freedom of expression as a fundamental right to all Indians. Bollywood has taken the full advantage of this right and has become a global brand to reckon with.¹ Indian entertainment industry is not limited to Hindi films only. It is interesting to note that process of economic liberalization and advent of TV channels coincided in India in 1991. Both phenomena became intertwined and worked as force multiplier for each other. Serials and advertisements on TV channels provided an ideological justification for economic liberalization. On the other hand, revenues generated by companies due to economic liberalization became a fodder for advertisements on TV. Serials like *Kyonki Saas bhi Kabhi Bahu Thi* and *Kahani Ghar Ghar Ki* became the household names. In 2000s, social networking sites caught the fancy of Indian youth. In 2010s, Facebook, Twitter and Instagram became a new fad. It became trendy to post any and everything on social networking sites. There is no doubt that these sites were used positively also for various social campaigns and causes but largely their use remained limited to online entertainment. In late 2010s, phenomenon of web-series emerged in India. What exactly is a web series? Web-series is basically a narrative told in the form of episodes. In a way, it is very much like a TV series. But its availability is on Internet and all the episodes of a web-series are uploaded simultaneously on the Internet. Thus viewer does not have to wait for every week or every day to enjoy his episode. This has also created a phenomenon of binge watching in which viewer watches all the episodes without breaks. Binge watching a serious hazard to mental and physical health.²

The phenomenon of web-series had already been tested in western markets. Series like *Narcos*, *Black*

Mirror, House of Cards had become huge commercial success. With this Netflix and Amazon Prime had emerged as new media platforms, which challenged the traditional modes of movies and television series viewing and offered viewers the online platforms. This platform was far more private and intimate, because instead of group or family activity, entertainment consumption became an individual activity since viewers either utilized their laptops or mobile phones for watching online web-series.

In India also, web-series arrived in late 2010s. They immediately caught the attention of tech savvy Indian youth. Initial series like Sacred Games and Ghoul met with unprecedented success. After that there was a deluge of web-series. But web-series got the tremendous boost because of Covid 19. Since people were confined to their homes due to lockdown and there were no entertainment programs on TV because shooting the new episodes became impossible and simultaneously most sporting events were also cancelled, web series became the only option for time pass and entertainment.³ There was a race among producers like Netflix, Amazon Prime, Disney Hotstar, Zee Five, Voot, MX player etc. to launch new series. But in this competition, the quality of shows was seriously compromised. Although this paper argues that even initial web-series had the toxic cocktails of drugs, sex and violence but in later series even fig leaf was dropped and web series acquired porn like quality laced with expletives and scenes of people consuming drugs like cocaine, heroine, brown sugar and ecstasy. Extra-marital relations, free sex and portrayal of gay and lesbian relationships became the common themes of these web-series. This paper makes content and discourse analysis of these web-series and comes to the conclusion that time has come to impose censorship on these series. I would like to make it clear at this point that I have no objections to the use of expletives and portrayal of drugs, sex and violence in web-series if it is done according to the demand of

story and a clear disclaimer is added that is should be watched by adult viewers only. But my analysis points to the fact that the scenes of protagonists and antagonists consuming drugs alike, character indulging in sex only to titillate viewers and mindless violence to imitate slasher⁴ movies is dominating the themes of web-series which cannot be justified from any point of view. For this paper, I have made the content analysis of following web-series—

Sacred Games, Ghoul, Made in Heaven, Raktanchal, Apaharan, Bard of Blood, The Family Man, Mafia, Mumbai-The City of Dreams, Mirzapur, Inside Edge, Delhi Crimes, Special Ops, Ek This Begum and Asur.

A Brief History of Web-series in India

There have been many studies regarding the social, political and cultural effects of Bollywood on Indian society. In last two decades, effects of cable TV channels on Indian society have also been studied. There have been full-fledged studies of the impact of Internet and social networking sites on Indian society. But web-series still remains a comparatively new phenomenon in India. Interestingly, in a very short period, web-series have become a dominant form of entertainment in the country, eclipsing cinema and TV channels. Production companies and online platforms keenly observed the interest of Indian viewers in international web-series and then started serving Indian versions.

There remains a controversy regarding which was the first Indian web-series. Most people agree that Permanent Roommates produced by TVF in 2014 was the first web-series in India. The series was available for free on YouTube. It became hugely popular with younger audience because of its informal dialogues and good theme. For next couple of years, similar kinds of web-series were released in India. It was not a commercial venture at that time. Series makers were motivated more by the sense of creative satisfaction than by commercial profits. Inside Edge, released in 2017, by Amazon Prime is considered to be first commercial Indian web-

series, although a foreign network produced it. Amazon followed this experiment by its next series *Breathe*. But it was with *Sacred Games*, produced by Netflix in 2018, that web-series became a household word in India. *Sacred Games* established a new paradigm of entertainment in India. It was a huge commercial success for Netflix.⁵ It also set the tone and tenor for the content of future web-series in India. Very soon, Indian entertainment market was flooded with web-series. As mentioned earlier lockdown imposed due to Covid 19, proved to be a magic pill for web-series. Broadcast of TV serials and new shows was interrupted because of Corona. Consequently, viewers who were earlier not interested in the genre of web-series found themselves watching the web-series. There is no official data available but it is safe to assume that big portion of Indian viewers is hooked to web-series. International broadcasters like Netflix and Amazon Prime had already recognized the potential of Indian market. Now Indian online platforms also followed suit. Very soon, MX player and Zee Five flooded the Indian market with their own web-series. Now there are at least ten major online platform producing web-series in India. Many major production houses have cut deals with international online platforms to produce Indian content for them. Betaal, produced for Netflix by Indian production houses Red Chillies Entertainment and Blumhouse Productions is an example of this phenomenon. Thus Indian and foreign online platforms, Indian producers, actors, directors, technicians, advertisers and viewers, all have found a winning formula of web-series.

In such a short span, why have web-series emerged as dominant form of entertainment? The answer to this question lies in the ethos of Indian culture. Film going is a group activity in India. Most of the times whole families or group of friends make a plan to watch a film. Similarly, watching TV is also a family activity in India. Mostly whole families get together to watch their favorite soap opera. In such scenario if there is an explicit scene or an expletive is used, the

members of the group feel embarrassed. Parents and children could not watch such programs together. But laptops and mobile phones have provided a very intimate space for entertainment consumers. Now they can watch web-series filled with scenes of sex without being embarrassed in the privacy of the space created by their mobile phones or laptops. This has changed the entire paradigm of entertainment consumption in India.

A Content Analysis of Web-series in India

Content analysis is a process by which the theme, story and scenes of an artistic work are analyzed vertically and horizontally. Vertical analysis relates to the linear story and theme of the film, TV program or web series while horizontal analysis concentrates on decoding the messages of particular scenes. Discourse analysis concentrates basically on dialogues and tries to reveal the hidden and coded messages of language used in a work of art. This paper utilizes the methodologies of content and discourse analysis to understand the effect of web-series on Indian social system.

An Overdose of Drugs

Indian web-series are obsessed with drug use. Most of the characters are shown freely consuming substances like heroine and cocaine. The method of consuming drugs—making thin lines of cocaine or heroine and then snorting them—is shown in graphic detail. Most of the Indian youth, who are not unfamiliar with drug use, have seen the method of consuming drugs by these web-series. Most of the characters in most of the web-series are shown to be consuming drugs. As a matter of fact, substance abuse scenes are used to depict that a how 'cool' a particular character is. The evil effects of drug abuse on human health are never shown. It could appear that making a blanket statement like most of the characters in most of the web-series are shown to be drug abusers, is a gross generalization, but even a cursory look at any web-series would prove the point. In the series *Mafia*, a character actually says, "don't you people think of any thing else, just drugs and sex

and only drugs and sex.” She could not have been more correct because in Mafia, from beginning to end every character is either taking drugs or indulging in physical relationships. Rest of the scenes, are laced with liberal dollops of extreme violence. Showing a particular character using drugs may be a part of the story, but when almost every other character is consuming drugs, it is dangerous message for the youth of the country. These web-series portray that consuming drugs is a normal practice of uber cool life style. The basic contention here is that these web-series glamourize the use of drugs and indirectly tell the viewers that if you want a glitzy life style, use of drugs is a primary requirement. Most of the characters are shown to be using drugs and alcohol simultaneously. Medical fraternity has always warned that using drugs and alcohol together may lead to immediate fatality. Smoking and using alcohol is another marked feature of these web-series. Since these series are not censored, there is no requirement to add the warning that smoking and consumption of alcohol is injurious to health. Drunk and drugged characters are very much the part of space created by these web-series. Most of the web-series such as Sacred Games, Made in Heaven, Raktanchal, Mafia, Mubai-The City of Dreams and Rangbaaz have characters smoking, drinking and using drugs constantly. None of the series discusses or even mentions that there are severe health effects of smoking, drinking and drug abuse. For example, the lead character of Mubai-The City of Dreams is always drinking, smoking, using drugs and indulging in sex.

Web-Series and Hyper Sexual Themes

Mirzapur, a very popular web-series in India has a sidetrack of a younger woman who is sexually dissatisfied with an older husband. She develops a physical relationship with a servant. Ultimately, her father in law finds it out and rapes her as a punishment. And this is all shown in graphic details to titillate the voyeuristic tendencies of the viewer.⁶ Interestingly, all of this has nothing to do with the central plot of the story, which revolves around the gang war to dominate the

crime scene of city of Mirzapur. Mirzapur is just an example. Most of the web-series portray sex in graphic detail.⁷ It is assumed that viewer will lap up the pornographic content of the series.⁸ Series like Delhi Crime—based upon Nirbhaya case—is an exception, which depicts sexual violence against women for bringing social awareness. Sacred Games, which is called the mother of all web-series in India, has a hyper sexual theme running in parallel with the story. There are countless sex scenes in the series, which add nothing to the original plot of the web-series. Inside Edge, which became so popular, that producer churned out two seasons of the series, is also laced with the sexual scenes while the main theme of the series is match fixing in cricket. In order to titillate even further, web-series liberally portray sexual perversions in order to compete with other series and to become most talked about web-series among youngsters.

In India LGBT rights movement is at a critical juncture. Supreme Court has decriminalized gay sex and at this time it is important to present visual image of lesbian and gay community with great deal of sensitivity in order to bring LGBT community in mainstream. But there is a race among web-series to portray gay and lesbian community in a stereotypical manner, which is exactly what LGBT community does not need. Made in Heaven has a gay protagonist whose sexual relationship are shown in graphic detail. Again the theme of the web-series is about a company, which organizes marriages for rich clients. Gay relationships of the protagonist have nothing to do with main story. Similarly gays scenes of Sacred Games add nothing to the main story. In Mumbai-The City of Dreams portray a protagonist in lesbian relationship. But the series is about fight between a brother and a sister after their father is shot. The argument here is that LGBT community needs to be portrayed poignantly and realistically. But these series leave no opportunity to depict lesbians and gays in stereotypical fashion and make a caricature of entire community.

A Cult of Violence

In *Sacred Games*, Ganesh Gaitonde, the protagonist, kills 80 Muslims randomly in a day. There is no bigger example of mindless violence and gore in India web-series. Violence is not only justified, it is also glorified. Extreme violence, reminding the slasher movies of Hollywood, has become the favorite tool of makers of web-series. In *Asur* a doctor autopsies the body of his own wife, but she has been so badly disfigured that he is not able to recognize her. Series like *Bard of Blood* and *The Family Man* take viewers to Afghanistan and Pakistan where whatever violent methods protagonist uses are justified since he is exterminating fundamentalists, the ultimate evil. Web-series like *Rangbaaz*, *Bhaukal* and *Mirzapur* take a mafia don as a protagonist. Off course he dies in the end but the entire film is shown from his perspective. His life style, his violent streak, his command over his group and his willingness to use extreme violence against his enemies are the basic themes running through the movie. Usually these web-series take a sympathetic view of the muscleman hero and try to portray him as the victim of the circumstances. It is shown that he had no option left but to become a mafia don. Viewers' sympathy usually lies with the mafia don. The glorification of gangster may have serious effect on the thinking of youngsters. The muscleman is usually shown very kind and humble to the poor people. Like in *Ek Thi Begum*, the gangster is shown to be a very good human being and it is the police, which are vilified. Similarly, in *Mumbai-The City of Dreams*, as mentioned earlier, a sister kills her own brother without regret, politicians are vilified and it is shown that the protagonist has done the very correct thing by killing her own sibling. In *Sacred Games*, *Bard of Blood*, *The Family Man* and *Mirzapur*, bullets fly constantly; blood splatters and highly sophisticated weapons are shown off. There is so much violence that viewers become numb to it.

Other Themes Running Through Web-Series

Apart from this, there are certain other themes running through these web-series. Most of the

web-series are set in Uttar Pradesh or Bihar. May be the criminalization of politics in these states makes them the perfect setting for Mafia genre of web-series. Most of the web-series use colloquial Hindi as their lingua franca. There is special attempt to use as many expletives as possible. Series like *Raktanchal* has expletives woven in almost every dialogue. Stories are usually shown from male point of view. Women mostly play only decorative part in the story. Series like *Delhi Crime* and *Ek Thi Begum* are exception to this rule. It is usually shown that politicians use criminals to attain their own ends and when their objectives are met, they ruthlessly order police to kill the criminals. The problem with this idea is that criminal is idolized in the young mind. It is almost never gangsters' fault. This raises his status to the cult level. Many characters are shown so mentally unhinged that violence is only expected of them. For example, in *Mafia* the killer is shown to be completely unhinged. There is absolutely no attempt to understand mental problems sympathetically.

Suggestions

There is absolutely no doubt that these web-series are having negative effects on young minds. Even older viewers are hooked to these series, although they may be better able to handle the negative effects of these web-series. There is an immediate need to frame a law governing the making of these web-series. Bringing web-series under the purview of Information and Broadcast Ministry is the step in right direction.¹⁰ However, government should issue strict guidelines for the makers of these web-series. Although best option would have been that the makers of these web series should have self censored the content and then there would have been no need to involve government but sadly series makers have failed in this responsibility miserably. These web-series should be immediately brought in the purview of censor board.¹¹ There is no logic to argue that it would curtail freedom of expression in the country. After all, films also have to go through censor board.¹² If anyone has a problem with the

decision of censor board, that decision can be challenged in the courts. There is absolutely no reason why these web-series should not show warnings that use of drugs, cigarettes and alcohol is injurious to health. Popularity of web-series among youngsters makes them a powerful medium of social messaging and change. Web-series like Kota Factory and Pitchers are examples of the power of web-series. There is a need to understand that entertainment and social messaging are not contradictory. It is possible to make a successful web-series with positive social message. Although it is difficult and demands hard work while serving the cocktail of drugs, violence and sex is far easier. This also means that parents and guardians have a great responsibility to check what the teenagers of their family are watching.

Conclusion

This paper has analyzed the new phenomenon of web-series in India. It has made a content and discourse analysis of some popular web-series. This paper concludes that these web-series have become immensely popular in a very short time. This genre of entertainment is different because it does not involve a group activity like film and television watching. People watch these web-series in their intimate space via mobile phone or laptop. Makers of these web-series have used his intimate space to provide a lethal cocktail of violence, drugs and sex. Youngsters are being severely affected by these web-series. There is an immediate need to bring these web-series under the purview of censor board. Society should come forward to boycott the web-series, which almost promote drugs, sex and violence as a lifestyle. Probably this could be the greatest deterrent to the makers of these web-series.

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